

MOHC PPE experiments

Data from two perturbed physics ensembles developed by the Met Office Hadley Centre as part of the QUMP (Quantifying Uncertainty in Model Predictions) project. These data were used to investigate changes in African temperature and precipitation associated with global warming for a special issue on the future of African rainforests [1].

Note that these differ from the perturbed physics ensemble provided at:
http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/data_browser/data_browser/badc/hadcm3

Data are provided in NetCDF format.

- 1) **HadSM3 2xCO₂ experiments (AS-PPE):** 280 versions of HadSM3, which has the same atmospheric and land surface physics as HadCM3, but with a 50m thermodynamic mixed layer or “slab” ocean. Each model version was run in equilibrium experiments, with preindustrial (“Cntl”) and doubled CO₂ (“DCO2”). The runs continue for 20 years after equilibrium and the data provided here are 20 year monthly and seasonal means from this period.

The ensemble was constructed in three stages (S-PPE-S, S-PPE-M, and S-PPE-E in [2]). The first 52 versions were created via single and multiple parameter perturbations [3]. The next 100 members were developed using results from the first stage to produce credible model variants tuned to observations [4]. The remaining versions were designed to create an emulator which could predict climate response across all possible combinations of parameter values [5]. Barnett et al. [6] describe the parameterisations and range of expert values.

In James et al. [1], some model versions were excluded from the analysis, but the remaining ensemble members are included in this dataset in separate directories. 140 model versions with top of atmosphere flux imbalances $>5 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ were removed, and these are stored in the “flux_constraint” directory. 28 model versions with entrainment coefficients outside the likely range (<2 or >4) were also excluded, and these are stored in the “ent_constraint” directory, leaving 112 members in the “subensemble”.

- 2) **HadCM3 SRES A1FI experiments (AO-PPE):** 17 versions of HadCM3. The 17 parameter combinations were chosen from the possible 280 explored in AS-PPE, and then coupled to a dynamical ocean. Each model version was run in transient experiments: a 150 year control run with preindustrial (1860) forcings (“CM_Cntl”), and SRES A1FI (“A1FI”). One of the 17 versions has the standard parameterisations of HadCM3, and this version is identical to that included in CMIP3 except for the addition of flux adjustments and an interactive sulphur cycle.

The parameter combinations are the same as those used for the HadCM3 experiment run in SRES A1B, available here:

http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/data_browser/data_browser/badc/hadcm3

Historical runs for the same model versions are also available via this link, and this table shows the mapping between the model name (“runid”) for the historical run and the runid for the A1B run:

http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/hadcm3/hadcm3_experiment_lookup.html

A table is provided below to add the runids for the CM_Cntl and A1FI experiments.

In James et al. [1], 4 model versions with entrainment coefficients >4 were removed. As with AS-PPE, these are included here in a separate directory (“ent_constraint”) from the 13 ensemble members used for the analysis (“subensemble”).

Directory structure

Directory: /badc/link/data/misc/qump_oxford/\$base/\$constraint/\$scen/\$runid/\$stream/\$stash/

File: \$base.\$scen.\$runid.\$stream.\$stash.nc

\$base hadsm3 or hadcm3

\$constraint distinguishes the subensemble from models removed with the flux_constraint or ent_constraint (described above)

\$scen scenario: Cntl or DCO2 for HadSM3, CM_Cntl or A1FI for HadCM3

\$runid runid or model name. For HadSM3 these are numbers 0001 to 0280. For HadCM3 there are specific runid's for each experiment, as shown below:

	CM_Cntl	A1FI	HadSM3
0	aenwp	Agnhs	59
1	afcra	Agnha	88
2	afcrb	Agnhb	125
3	afcrc	Agnhc	75
4	afcrd	Agnhd	77
5	afcrf	Agnhf	93
6	afcrh	Agnhh	181
7	afcri	Agnhi	154
8	afcrj	Agnhj	97
9	afcrk	Agnhk	168
10	afcrl	Agnhl	99
11	afcrm	Agnhm	152
12	afcrn	Agnhn	158
13	afcro	Agnho	135
14	afcrp	Agnhp	139
15	afcrq	Agnhq	167
16	afcrr	Agnhr	92

\$stream for HadSM3 “000001” is 20 year monthly mean data and “000003” is 20 year seasonal mean data (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON). For HadCM3 apm is atmospheric monthly data.

\$stash stash code or variable. The table below indicates the variables available.

Stash code	Variable	HadSM3 availability	HadCM3 availability
03.236	Temperature at 1.5m	20y monthly	monthly
05.216	Precipitation rate	20y monthly	monthly
00.024	Surface temperature	20y monthly	
15.222	Omega at 500hPa	20y monthly	
16.222	Sea level pressure	20y monthly	
15.201	U wind at 5 levels	20y seasonal	
15.202	V wind at 5 levels	20y seasonal	
15.226	Specific humidity at 5 levels	20y seasonal	
01.207	Incoming short wave radiation at TOA	20y seasonal	
01.208	Outgoing short wave radiation at TOA	20y seasonal	
02.205	Outgoing long wave radiation at TOA	20y seasonal	

References

1. James, R., Washington, R. and Rowell, D. P. Implications of global warming for the climate of African rainforests, submitted to *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society, B: Biological Sciences*, October 2012.
2. Collins, M., Booth, B. B. B., Glen, B. B., James, R. H., Sexton, D. M. H., & Webb, M. J. (2010). Climate model errors, feedbacks and forcings: a comparison of perturbed physics and multi-model ensembles. *Climate Dynamics*. doi:10.1007/s00382-010-0808-0
3. Murphy, J. M., Sexton, D. M. H., Barnett, D. N., Jones, G. S., Webb, M. J., Collins, M., & Stainforth, D. A. (2004). Quantification of modelling uncertainties in a large ensemble of climate change simulations. *Nature*, 430 769-772. doi:10.1038/nature02770.1.
4. Webb, M. J., Senior, C. a., Sexton, D. M. H., Ingram, W. J., Williams, K. D., Ringer, M. a., McAvaney, B. J., et al. (2006). On the contribution of local feedback mechanisms to the range of climate sensitivity in two GCM ensembles. *Climate Dynamics*, 27(1), 17-38. doi:10.1007/s00382-006-0111-2
5. Rougier, J., Sexton, D. M. H., Murphy, J. M., & Stainforth, D. (2009). Analyzing the Climate Sensitivity of the HadSM3 Climate Model Using Ensembles from Different but Related Experiments. *Journal of Climate*, 22(13), 3540-3557. doi:10.1175/2008JCLI2533.1
6. Barnett, D. N., Brown, S. J., Murphy, J. M., Sexton, D. M. H., & Webb, M. J. (2006). Quantifying uncertainty in changes in extreme event frequency in response to doubled CO2 using a large ensemble of GCM simulations. *Climate Dynamics*, 26(5), 489-511. doi:10.1007/s00382-005-0097-1